

PES SOLVENT RESISTANCE ENHANCED BY NANOSIZED PARTICLES

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SUMMARY

PES is an high performance polymer characterized by good toughness, elevated glass transition and heat distortion temperatures. Nevertheless because of its poor solvent resistance, it is not widely employed in many applications, such as aeronautical composites. In this work continuous fibre composites with nanofilled PES matrix were produced. The nanoparticles increased the PES matrix solvent resistance and influenced the mechanical properties of the composites.

Keywords: Polyethersulphone, nanoparticle, solvent resistance, thermoplastic matrix composites, dynamical-mechanical properties

ABSTRACT

PES is an high performance thermoplastic polymer, but its applications are limited by poor resistance to several classes of solvents [1]. Its resistance to solvents was improved adding nanofillers to the polymer [2]. Silica and graphite nanoparticles were used to prepare PES nanocomposites by hot-mixing technique and dynamical mechanical properties of the nanocomposites were tested with DMA. The nanofillers dispersion was analyzed by means of an electronic microscope while the solvent resistance of PES nanocomposites was investigated with two different tests: 1) weight increase due to methylene chloride absorption in a saturated atmosphere; 2) time scan of the storage modulus of specimens immersed in a acetone bath. Furthermore the prepared nanocomposites were used to produce thermoplastic matrix continuous fibres composites by using the film stacking technique. The solvent resistance of the composites was evaluated measuring the variation of mechanical properties after their immersion in acetone.

Experimental

The PES Ultrason E3010 was supplied by BASF. The silica nanoparticles Aerosil R380 were furnished by Degussa. A proprietary expanded graphite particles (TG-741) were supplied by GrafTech International (TG-741 and its availability exclusively from GrafTech International Holdings, Inc.). The glass fibres woven fabric used as

reinforcement was the VR32 type produced by Teximpianti (330 g/m², warp/weft 6.5/5.5).

The graphite and silica particles were mixed separately with PES in a Haake Rheocord internal mixer at 320°C (30RPM, 5 min, excluded feeding time) and different nanocomposite matrices with several filler contents (0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.5 % volume) were produced.

Preliminary evaluations of the solvent absorption were carried out measuring the weight gain of samples in saturated atmosphere of methylene chloride according to standard ASTM D543-95.

The nanocomposite PES matrices were used to prepare fibre reinforced composite by the film stacking process. Eight layers of glass fibre fabrics were stacked between nine layers of PES films in a closed mould and then inserted in a hydraulic hot press (Collin GmbH, model P 300P), which was able to control the temperature and pressure profiles applied to the mould.

Dynamical mechanical tests were carried out by means of a Triton DMA Tritec 2000 in tensile deformation at 1 Hz frequency heating the samples at rate of 4°C/min. In order to evaluate the solvent absorption process in the polymeric matrices tensile DMA testes were performed on samples immersed in a acetone bath at 30°C.

The nanoparticle distribution in the polymeric matrix and the fracture surface of the glass fibre composites were analyzed with both optical microscope (Olympus BX51) and scanning electron microscope (Leica S440).

Mechanical flexural tests were carried out using a SANS 3310 universal testing machine on samples cut from the composites panels, according to ASTM D790, at room temperature. Five specimens from each composite panel were tested and the average values and standard deviation were calculated from the measured data.

The glass fibres content of composites was evaluated from density data obtained in accordance with standard ASTM D792.

Results and Discussions

Dynamical mechanical properties

The storage modulus of PES+R380 nanocomposites was lower than that of pure PES matrix for all silica contents samples, excluded the PES+0.1%vol R380 that presented a slight modulus enhancement. In turn DMA tests on PES+TG-741 specimens evidenced an increase of storage modulus with the filler content, except, also in this case, the sample containing 0.1% volume fraction of nanoparticles that presented a storage modulus enhancement comparable to that of PES+2.5 TG-741 sample. The peculiar behaviour of the low filler concentration samples could be related to the particles distribution in PES matrix (the lower filler content during the mixing process led to a better particle dispersion reducing the agglomerate presence respect to higher concentration nanocomposites). The storage modulus of PES+TG-741 matrices was higher than that of PES+R380 evidencing the effect of particle aspect ratio on the elastic properties. In fact, as widely reported in the studies on particulate composite [3-5], the modulus of reinforced matrices increases with the aspect ratio of the filler (at constant

filler content); hence the higher aspect ratio of graphite particles (planar), compared to that of the silica (spherical), resulted in higher stiffening of the PES.

SEM and Light Microscope analysis

SEM image of fracture surface of nanocomposites samples containing 0.1% volume of filler are shown in Fig. 1. The dimension of particles clusters in the PES+0.1% R380 sample were not larger than 300 nm (Fig. 1-a) while PES+0.1%TG-741 matrix presented a wider distribution of particles dimensions (from 10-20 micron to 200-300 nm) as can be observed in Fig. 1-b where a large graphite particle (about 10 micron) protruded from the matrix in the centre of the picture and smaller ones are embedded on the left side (300-400 nm). Silica nanoparticles showed an higher interaction with PES matrix than graphite particles since they were completely embedded in the matrix. Evident detached surface, in fact, between matrix and particle surrounded the bigger graphite particles (Fig. 1-b).

Fig. 1. SEM image of fracture surface of the PES+0.1%R380 sample(a); SEM image of the fracture surface of PES+0.1%TG-741 sample (b).

The investigation by light microscope of the reinforced composites showed that glass fibres were homogeneously distributed and thoroughly wetted by the polymer, as illustrated in Fig. 2 where the rubbed surface of neat PES matrix composite is reported.

Fig. 2. Image from light microscope of rubbed surface of neat PES-glass fibre composite.

Solvent absorption

In order to estimate the effect of nanofillers on the solvent absorption behaviour of the nanocomposite samples, two kinds of tests were performed: 1) solvent uptake test in saturated atmosphere of methylene chloride and 2) time scan of storage modulus variation of samples steeped in a acetone bath. The first test provided an estimation of the solvent absorption rate of the polymeric samples, while the second one evaluated the decay of elastic properties due to solvent penetration in the matrix. In Fig. 3 the results of the solvent uptake test are reported. PES+0.5%R380 and PES+1.0% R380 specimens showed a reduction of 80% of the solvent uptake compared to neat PES sample in the early stages of the experiment. The weight gain of PES+2.5 R380 matrix is higher than the other nanocomposites but smaller than that of pure PES in all investigated timeframe. The solvent uptake of the graphite based nanocomposites was smaller than the silica filled samples (Fig. 3-b) and did not exceed the value of 2% during the experiment (the uptake of silica based matrices rose above 2% after 300 minutes). The addition of nanofillers in the matrix reduced the diffusivity of the solvent in the PES matrix; this effect was more evident for samples loaded with graphite particles probably due to their lamellar structure respect to silica particles which have spherical shape. However the barrier properties did not increase with the filler content in the matrix; this behaviour could indicate that the dispersions and distributions of the particles were not constant at the different particles contents.

Fig. 3. Methylene chlorlyde uptake by silica R380 (a) and graphite TG-741 (b) based PES nanocomposite.

The results of the DMA time scan performed on polymeric samples steeped in acetone are illustrated in Fig. 4. The storage modulus decay is related to the solvent diffusion process in the polymeric matrix; such process is depending on both time and specimen dimensions, hence time values (Fig. 4) were divided by the cross sectional area of each tested specimen (rectangular cross section shape) in order to reduce the size effects of the samples in the data interpretation. The modulus decreased regularly until a drop related caused by the plasticization of the matrix for all sample. The modulus of the neat PES dropped off after 66 min/mm² while the other nanofilled matrices showed the elastic properties slump at higher normalized times. Only the PES+2.5%R380 sample plasticized at reduced time. PES+0.5TG-741 and PES+0.5R380 presented plasticization respectively at 102 and 109 min/mm².

The time to reach plasticization of the samples containing 0.5% of nanoparticles doubled respect to neat PES one. Both solvent absorption tests indicated that the

addition of nanoparticles to the PES matrix reduced the diffusivity of the solvents but their solubility was substantially unchanged considering that plasticization occurs in all sample. In methylene chloride uptake tests the graphite based nanocomposites showed a higher barrier properties (particle shape effect), while the time scan DMA experiments evidenced that the samples with 0.5% vol particles took twice as long to plasticize when compared to the neat PES sample. The curve related to the PES +2.5%TG-741 sample was not reported since catastrophic failures occurred after the immersion in the acetone. The low solvent resistance of the samples containing 2.5% of nanofiller could be caused by particles clusters formed in the matrix that allowed a percolation path of the solvent and by their inhomogeneous distribution in the matrix.

Fig. 4. Time scan DMA tests in tensile deformation mode (1 Hz, 0.1% strain amplitude, 30°C), on samples immersed in acetone bath. The time axis is normalized dividing by the cross section area of the samples.

Mechanical tests

Glass fibre composites were prepared by using the film stacking technique; the total amount of glass fibres and polymeric films utilized and the processing parameters (temperature and pressure profiles) were kept constant for all the composites. The matrix viscosity increased with nanofiller content and the squeezing out of the matrix during the consolidation process reduced at higher nanoparticles content. Hence the glass fibre volume fraction in the composites decreased with the amount of nanofillers in the matrix, as illustrated in Fig. 5-a.

Two composites with neat PES matrix were produced stacking different amounts of matrix in order to produce two neat matrix composites with different glass fibres content. These composites allowed to evaluate the influence of the reinforcement fraction in the pure matrix composite (in every graph there are two values in correspondence of neat PES, representing the samples containing 56 and 43 % glass fibres volume fraction).

Flexural test were performed on flat specimens cut from the composite panels; the test strain rate and the span-to-depth ratio were respectively 0.01 mm/mm/min and 16:1. The flexural modulus of elasticity increased with the amount of reinforcement as illustrated in Fig. 5-b; the nanoparticles in the matrix induced a stiffening effect in the composite more evident for graphite based compositions. The flexural strength also presented a dependence upon both fibres contents and nanoparticles typologies (Fig. 5-c); the composite containing graphite showed the highest strength (0.1 and 2.5 % vol graphite). The flexural elastic modulus and strength of neat PES composite containing 56% vol of fibres (although the most reinforced) showed an anomalous behaviour: the smallest elastic modulus but elevated strength. These trends could be due to the higher anisotropy of these composite respect to the other as explained in the standard ASTM D790. In fact “shear deflections can seriously reduce the apparent modulus of highly anisotropic composites when they are tested at low span-to-depth ratios and a span-to-depth ratio of 60 to 1 is recommended for flexural modulus determinations. While flexural strength should be determined on a separate set of replicate specimens at a lower that induces tensile failure in the outer fibres of the beam along its lower surface” [text reported from the ASTM D790 standard].

Fig. 5. a) Glass fibres volume fraction of composites vs nanoparticles fraction in matrix. b) Flexural modulus of glass fibre composites at room temperature. c) Flexural strength of glass fibre composites at room temperature.

The modulus and the strength determinations were carried out on the same specimen and the span-to-depth ratio was kept constantly equal to 16:1. Nevertheless the evaluated flexural modulus and strength are very close to data reported in technical [6] and scientific [7] literature about glass fibres composites with polyphenylenesulfone (PPS) matrix (Ryton PPS E-Glass/Satin 60% vol – Flexural Modulus= 21 GPa –

Flexural Strength=366 MPa), which is a high performance thermoplastic polymer with mechanical properties similar to PES.

The composite samples were steeped in acetone for 5 days at controlled temperature of 30°C and, after conditioning, were tested to evaluate the reduction of mechanical properties caused by solvent absorption. The flexural modulus lowered in all composites as clearly illustrated in Fig. 6, where the mechanical properties showed a very steep decay.

A slight dependence upon matrix content in the neat PES composite is evidenced by the higher modulus of 42.5% vol glass fibres PES sample respect to the other neat PES composite (56% vol glass fibres); this behaviour could be related to the not completion of absorption process in the 42.5% vol glass fibres PES sample because of its higher matrix amount. Graphite based matrix composites showed a superior resistance to acetone, as evidenced by the flexural modulus always higher than the corresponding of silica bases matrix composites. The nanofillers, as explained in the solvent absorption section, induced a decrease of the solvent diffusivity in the matrix but not a substantial reduction of the solubility. Hence the main effect of particles was a delay of the mechanical properties decay of the samples exposed to solvents.

Fig. 6. Flexural modulus of glass fibre composites at room temperature before and after immersion in acetone for 5 day at 30°C.

Conclusions

PES nanocomposites were prepared by mixing the polymeric matrix with two different nanofillers: silica and graphite. Both fillers induced an improvement of barrier properties in PES matrices, reducing the diffusivity of acetone and methylene chloride, as demonstrated by solvent absorption tests. The nanocomposites were employed as matrices to produce continuous glass fibres composites through film stacking technique. The viscosity increase of the nanofilled PES led to the reduction of glass fibres fraction in the composite since manufacturing parameters were kept constant for all samples;

hence the higher was the nanoparticles content in the matrix (the higher the viscosity) the smaller was the glass fibres fraction in the composites.

The flexural mechanical tests showed a clear dependence of elastic modulus upon glass fibre contents. At constant fibre content the graphite nanoparticles in the matrix induced a higher stiffening effect with respect to silica ones. The flexural strength resulted more influenced by the nanoparticles and in particular glass fibre composites with matrix containing graphite showed the highest flexural strength. The mechanical flexural properties of composite specimens immersed in acetone for 5 days steeply decreased (graphite matrix composites presented bit higher modulus) indicating that, even though the nanofillers increased the barrier properties of the matrix, they were not able to improve thoroughly the resistance to long time exposure to solvents. Nevertheless the obtained results attest that the addition of nanofillers to polymeric matrices can extend their barrier properties and further improvements could be achieved working on both matrix/nanoparticles interface properties and particles distribution.

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